

A Note on the Lower Bound for the Independence Number of a Graph

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Abstract

Let G be a graph. A set of vertices in G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . In this short note, we present a lower bound for the independence number of a graph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges. For each vertex $v \in V(G)$, we use $N_G(v)$ to denote all the vertices in G which are adjacent to v . The degree of a vertex v in $V(G)$, denoted $d_G(v)$, is defined as

$|N_G(v)|$. A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number of a graph G , denoted $\alpha(G)$, is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G .

Caro [2] and Wei [4] obtained the following lower bound for a graph. See also [3].

Theorem 1 Let G be a graph with n vertices. Then

$$\alpha(G) \geq \sum_{v \in V(G)} \frac{1}{d_G(v) + 1}$$

with equality if and only if G is a union of disjoint complete graphs.

In this short note, we, based on the Theorem 1, obtain a simple lower bound for the independence number of a graph.

Theorem 2 Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. If the maximum degree of G is Δ , then

$$\alpha \geq \frac{\sqrt{((\Delta + 2)e - n)^2 + 4ne} - ((\Delta + 2)e - n)}{2}$$

with equality if and only if G is an empty graph or a union of disjoint edges.

2 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 2. Let I be any maximum independent set in G . Then $|I| = \alpha$. Thus

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = |E(I, V - I)| \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Since $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = 2e$, we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) \leq e \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Set $I = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\alpha\}$. Applying AM-GM-HM inequalities for $d(u_1) + 1, d(u_2) + 1, \dots, d(u_\alpha) + 1$, we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} \frac{1}{d(u) + 1} \geq \frac{|I|^2}{\sum_{u \in I} (d(u) + 1)} \geq \frac{\alpha^2}{e + \alpha}.$$

By Theorem 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &\geq \sum_{v \in V} \frac{1}{d(v) + 1} = \sum_{u \in I} \frac{1}{d(u) + 1} + \sum_{u \in V-I} \frac{1}{d(u) + 1} \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha^2}{e + \alpha} + \sum_{u \in V-I} \frac{1}{\Delta + 1} = \frac{\alpha^2}{e + \alpha} + \frac{n - \alpha}{\Delta + 1}. \end{aligned}$$

Solving the inequality, we have

$$\alpha(G) \geq \frac{\sqrt{((\Delta + 2)e - n)^2 + 4ne} - ((\Delta + 2)e - n)}{2}.$$

Suppose

$$\alpha(G) = \frac{\sqrt{((\Delta + 2)e - n)^2 + 4ne} - ((\Delta + 2)e - n)}{2}.$$

From the previous proofs, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \sum_{v \in V} \frac{1}{d(v) + 1}, \\ \sum_{u \in I} \frac{1}{d(u) + 1} &= \frac{|I|^2}{\sum_{u \in I} (d(u) + 1)} = \frac{\alpha^2}{e + \alpha}, \\ \sum_{u \in V-I} \frac{1}{d(u) + 1} &= \sum_{u \in V-I} \frac{1}{\Delta + 1} = \frac{n - \alpha}{\Delta + 1}. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 1, we have that

G is a union of disjoint complete graphs,

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e = |E(I, V - I)| = \sum_{v \in V-I} d(v),$$

$$d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\alpha),$$

and the degree of each vertex in $V - I$ is equal to Δ .

Since $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e = |E(I, V - I)| = \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v)$, $V - I$ must be independent.

If $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\alpha) = 0$, then $0 = \sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e = |E(I, V - I)| = \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v)$. Thus $d(v) = 0$ for each $v \in V - I$. Hence G is an empty graph.

If $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\alpha) \neq 0$, then we claim that $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\alpha) = 1$. Suppose, to the contrary, that $d(u_1) = d(u_2) = \dots = d(u_\alpha) \geq 2$. This implies that there are two vertices in $N(u_1) \cap (V - I)$ such that they are not adjacent. Since G is a union of disjoint complete graphs, u_1 is a vertex of a complete graph. Thus all vertices in $N(u_1)$ are in the same complete graph and all vertices in $N(u_1)$ are pairwise adjacent, a contradiction. Similarly, we can prove that $d(v) = 1$ for each $v \in V - I$. Notice now that $\alpha = \sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e = |E(I, V - I)| = \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = n - \alpha$. Thus $\alpha = \frac{n}{2}$ and G is a union of disjoint edges.

If G is an empty graph, then $e = 0$ and

$$\alpha = n = \frac{\sqrt{((\Delta + 2)e - n)^2 + 4ne} - ((\Delta + 2)e - n)}{2}.$$

If G is a union of disjoint edges, then $e = \frac{n}{2}$, $\Delta = 1$, and

$$\alpha = \frac{n}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{((\Delta + 2)e - n)^2 + 4ne} - ((\Delta + 2)e - n)}{2}.$$

Remark 1. Clearly, the lower bound for the independence number of a graph in Theorem 2 is not as good as the one in Theorem 1. But, for a graph of a given order n , computing the lower bound for the independence number of a graph in Theorem 2 needs the degrees of all vertices in the graph and computing the lower bound for the independence number of a graph in Theorem 2 just needs the number of edges and the maximum degree of the graph.

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